

Challenges of Learning to Write Properly in English**Abdiganiyeva Go'zalxon Oxunjon qizi****ISFT, English teacher.****adganiyevaguzalxon@gmail.com****Annotation**

Writing is a fundamental communication skill, but learning how to write properly in English presents various challenges for both native and non-native speakers. This paper explores the complexities of mastering English writing, highlighting the issues of grammar, vocabulary, cultural differences, and the influence of technology. Through an examination of existing literature and educational strategies, this article aims to identify the primary obstacles learners face and suggest methods to improve English writing instruction.

Key words: Writing Skills, Teaching and Learning Writing, Challenges, Elementary School, English as a Second Language

Annotatsiya

Yozish asosiy kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalaridan biri hisoblanadi, ammo ingliz tilida to'g'ri yozishni o'rganish ham ona tilida so'zlashuvchilar, ham ona tili bo'lmaganlar uchun turli qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi. Ushbu maqola ingliz tilida yozishni egallashdagi murakkabliklarni o'rganadi, grammatik qoidalar, lug'at boyligi, madaniy farqlar va texnologiyaning ta'siri kabi muammolarni ta'kidlaydi. Mavjud adabiyot va ta'lim strategiyalari tahlili orqali ushbu maqola o'quvchilarning duch keladigan asosiy to'siqlarini aniqlash va ingliz tilida yozishni o'rgatishni yaxshilash usullarini taklif qilishni maqsad qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Yozuv ko'nikmalari, Yozishni o'rgatish va o'rganish, Qiyinchiliklar, Boshlang'ich Maktab, Ingliz tilini Ikkinchi Til sifatida.

Аннотация

Письмо - это фундаментальный навык общения, но обучение правильному письму на английском языке представляет различные сложности как для носителей языка, так и для тех, кто изучает его как иностранный. В данной статье исследуются сложности освоения письменного английского, подчеркиваются проблемы, связанные с грамматикой, словарным запасом, культурными различиями и влиянием технологий. Путем анализа существующей литературы и образовательных стратегий данная статья стремится выявить основные препятствия, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся, и предложить методы улучшения преподавания письма на английском языке.

Ключевые слова: навыки письма, преподавание и обучение письму, трудности, начальная школа, английский как второй язык

English is recognized as a global language and is highly sought after in today's world. It is the most commonly spoken language across the globe. However, writing in English remains a significant challenge for students learning it as a second language. Enhancing students' writing skills is one of the key obstacles that ESL teachers encounter in many schools today. Writing has long been a major hurdle for students learning English, particularly at the elementary level. Additionally, teachers also face various difficulties in teaching writing skills to elementary school students. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the challenges experienced by both students and teachers in the process of learning and teaching writing skills in elementary schools.

English serves as a lingua franca across the world, facilitating communication among individuals from diverse cultural, ethnic, and social backgrounds (Dewi, 2015). Among English teachers, the ability to teach writing effectively at the elementary level is crucial. Writing is a core aspect of English instruction and is introduced early, as students begin learning how to correctly form letters. A weak foundation in writing can lead to significant negative impacts on students' academic success. Writing is not only essential for academic growth but also plays a role in students' social and emotional development. In today's competitive environment, strong writing skills are vital for success, and an inability to write well may limit students' future job prospects. Consequently, it is important to address this

issue effectively. Writing is an essential skill that will benefit students throughout their lives. Introducing engaging writing activities in schools can boost students' confidence and encourage a long-term passion for writing. Early on, writing skills are particularly important for young students as they support learning across all academic subjects, enhance communication, and aid in self-expression.

Writing exercises not only improve penmanship but also contribute to overall academic growth by fostering problem-solving and critical thinking skills. The writing process—planning, researching, and revising—extends to other disciplines like Mathematics and Science. Additionally, writing helps expand general knowledge and vocabulary as a natural byproduct. Through journaling and personal storytelling, students can explore their identities and work through real-life challenges. According to a report by the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, writing can serve as a therapeutic outlet, offering students a way to cope with difficult situations, such as family issues or emotional struggles. Writing also plays a key role in students' social development. It helps them stay connected to the world around them by encouraging them to consider their audience and purpose. This practice enhances their verbal communication skills as well. Collaborative writing activities, where students give and receive feedback from peers, create opportunities for learning from one another. As students advance through their education, they will need to be both literate and digitally literate to succeed. While these skills complement each other, over-reliance on digital tools like spell checkers and grammar checkers can hinder the development of writing skills. For example, using a keyboard might prevent students from practicing their handwriting. It's important for students to understand that their own knowledge is crucial, as computers can make errors. In today's information-driven world, writers are in high demand to create digital content. Content writers are needed across various industries, especially in digital marketing. Companies, news websites, and social media marketing firms require skilled writers to craft content for a range of platforms, including brand messaging, advertisements, social media posts, blogs, and more.

One of the primary issues in learning to write in English is mastering its grammar. English grammar rules can be intricate and often counterintuitive, even for native speakers. Key difficulties include:

- **Tense Usage:** English has a wide range of tenses, and each one conveys subtle differences in meaning and time frame. For many learners, distinguishing between tenses (such as present perfect vs. past simple) can be confusing.
- **Word Order:** English is an SVO (Subject-Verb-Object) language, but there are many exceptions to this rule, especially when dealing with questions, conditionals, or emphatic statements.
- **Prepositions:** English prepositions are notoriously difficult to master because there are no universal rules governing their use. Learners often struggle with understanding which prepositions are appropriate in certain contexts (e.g., at the meeting, on the bus, in the car).

Each student encounters unique challenges when learning to write. Every student has their own strengths and weaknesses, which makes their learning experiences distinct. These challenges can hinder their progress in producing well-written pieces. The following sections outline some of the common difficulties students face in writing. A lack of vocabulary is one of the key issues students encounter when trying to develop their writing skills, as noted by Misbah et al. (2017). Vocabulary is a crucial component in constructing sentences, which form the foundation of effective writing (Asep, 2014). Students use both spoken and written words daily to express their thoughts, beliefs, and emotions. A strong vocabulary helps students communicate more clearly in both speaking and writing. The use of electronic dictionaries and increasing reading activities can assist students who struggle with limited vocabulary.

Poor spelling is another source of anxiety for students learning to write, as supported by Nyang'au Benard (2014). Strong spelling abilities contribute to successful writing development. Students who struggle with spelling often feel held back. Many students tend to spell words based on how they pronounce them, which can result in incorrect spelling, as Afrin (2016) pointed out. For instance, a student may spell "ballon" instead of "balloon."

According to Nyang'au Benard (2014), memorization techniques can help students improve their spelling skills.

Readiness is another challenge in learning writing, as noted by Foster (2015). Winarso (2016) emphasizes that readiness, whether physical or mental, is essential for successfully completing tasks. Without proper readiness, students may struggle with writing. If they are not mentally prepared, they may not be fully engaged in classroom learning. Foster (2015) suggests that motivating students and capturing their attention can enhance their readiness to learn writing.

Limited exposure to books and reading materials is another obstacle for elementary students in developing writing skills, as supported by Foster (2015). According to Muhammad Fareed et al. (2016), many students struggle to access sufficient and relevant sources of information. Without extensive reading, students may have difficulty crafting well-formed sentences or paragraphs. Since reading and writing are closely linked, a lack of reading material can lead to limited ideas and vocabulary for writing. Reading more helps students develop ideas and make connections with prior knowledge, fostering better writing. Foster (2015) explains that exposure to various reading materials raises language awareness.

Finally, lack of motivation is another challenge students face. Without motivation, students may lose interest in progressing with their learning. Motivation is critical for improving students' academic performance, as noted by Gbollie & Keamu (2017). Teachers can motivate students by offering positive reinforcement, such as simple phrases like "Good job!", "Nice try!", or "Keep it up!". Such encouragement can push students to further engage in their learning process.

Conclusion

Learning to write properly in English is a complex and ongoing process that requires a deep understanding of grammar, vocabulary, and cultural conventions. By addressing the common challenges learners face and employing effective pedagogical strategies, educators can help students develop strong, clear, and effective writing skills in English. Future

research should focus on developing more targeted instructional methods that cater to the specific needs of diverse learners in different linguistic and cultural contexts. By understanding the challenges faced by both students and teachers in the process of learning and teaching writing skills, educators can adopt the most effective strategies for instruction, offering valuable feedback and guidance. In addition, school management should address the obstacles teachers encounter, ensuring they have the necessary support to conduct an effective teaching process. Lastly, teachers can emphasize the importance of writing skills to inspire and motivate students to engage more deeply in learning them.

References

1. Abrar, M. (2016). Teaching English Problems: An Analysis of EFL Primary School Teachers in Kuala Tungkal. Birmingham.
2. Afrin, S. (2016). Writing Problems of Non-English Major Undergraduate Students in Bangladesh: An Observation. Open Journal of Social Sciences.
3. Anyiendah, M. S. (2017). Challenges Faced by Teachers When Teaching English in Public Primary Schools in Kenya.
4. Asep, S. (2014). The Challenges in Teaching Writing Skill at Junior High School: Problems and Solutions.
5. Dewi, A. (2015). Perception of English: A Study of Staff and Students at Universities in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Cambridge: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
6. Fareed, M., Ashraf, A., & Bilal, M. (2016). ESL Learners' Writing Skills: Problems, Factors and Suggestions. Journal of Education and Social Sciences.
7. Foster, B. (2015). Teaching Children with Reading and Writing Difficulties in Regular Schools.
8. Gbollie, C., & Keamu, H. P. (2017). Student Academic Performance: The Role of Motivation, Strategies, and Perceived Factors Hindering Liberian Junior and Senior High School Students Learning. Education Research.
9. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=97129#:~:text=Especially%20when%20it%20comes%20to,a%20good%20piece%20of%20writing.>

[10.https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374477115](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374477115) Process of Writing The Challenges in Writing Skill Among ESL Learners